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A Creative Folio

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The Breathtaking Gift of Life

The day began with the sun just peeking through the clouds as Ronaldo set out on his routine journey to work. The streets were bare, the wind brushed against his face, when out of nowhere a dog ran into the street.

"Not now!" Ronaldo said to himself, swerving to miss it.

The motorcycle slid on the ground. Tires squealed. He fell off the ground. It hurt to lift himself off the pavement.

Gripping his left arm, Ronaldo moaned, "Ahh... my shoulder."

The street was empty. There was no one. Gritting his teeth, Ronaldo managed to pull himself back on the motorcycle, and in pain, he said it to himself, "Just... make it to Jaro. No stopping now."

After what seemed an age, Ronaldo arrived at the police station. An officer intervened.

"Sir! What happened?"

"Accident... my shoulder," Ronaldo gasped weakly.

The officer immediately called for help. Soon, Ronaldo was on their way to St. Paul's Hospital.

A few hours later, Ronaldo lay in the stark white of the hospital's empty room after surgery, exhausted. His cousin, Ann, sat next to him, monitoring him nervously.

"Why do you think these things keep happening to you?" she asked quietly. "Four accidents. You must be used to it by now?"

Ronaldo gave a slight smile. "Maybe life's reminding me of something...something I keep forgetting."

Ann shook her head. A tear rolled down her cheek. "And what might that be?"

"That living is a gift," he said. "Whenever I wake up, whenever I hear someone laugh, even the pain... it means I'm still here. I forgot how to be thankful for that."

They were quiet for a moment. The heart monitor kept beeping steadily in the background.

"At this moment, you sound different," Ann said.

"Because everything feels different," Ronaldo said. "I look at people differently now...their lives, their problems, their joy... It's all the more important. Even the little things feel bigger, as though the smaller things seemed more meaningful than I previously thought."

Ann squeezed Ronaldo's hand slightly. "So what will you do?"

Ronaldo turned towards the window and looked out at the sunset as it disappeared. "Thank God for today. Value every breath. Live as if every moment really matters."

A soft smile touched Ann's lips. "There is a saying," she reminded him. "Life is not about the number of breaths we take, but rather the moments that take our breath away."

Ronaldo closed his eyes and said softly, "That's it. And this... this is one of those moments."